

The Developmental Characteristics Of The Five Social Beliefs Of The Terrorist Personality

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Abstract

The current research aims to identify the developmental characteristics of the social beliefs of the terrorist person, and to achieve the goal, the researcher used the Bond M.H., Leung K2011 scale. To verify the global validity of the scale, it was applied to a sample of 500 terrorists placed in Nasiriyah Central Prison. After verifying the validity of the scale, the basic factors for the cognitive axioms were extracted and five factors were (the equivalent irony for the effort flexibility versus religious fanaticism and belief in fate). The researcher reached a set of results, the most important of which are the prevalence of cynicism, exploitation, fanaticism, false religiosity, and belief in the inevitability of destiny and destiny. The researcher came up with a set of recommendations and suggestions.

1. Introduction

The issue of the struggle with terrorism is a problem in itself, while a larger problem arises in one of its most important aspects, which is the dismantling of the cognitive developmental characteristics and the intellectual and ideological background of these terrorist organizations. The issue of the trend of growth of social beliefs represents a big problem because it reflects on the behavior of terrorists and aims to manipulate trends For those beliefs they have and attract them, as the process of forming convictions is the first and most dangerous problem in engaging with these groups. The problem of the current research lies in arriving at the developmental and cognitive characteristics of the specific axioms of terrorist behavior who practiced, worked, and became involved with those organizations and knowing the vectors of those axioms.

The problem of the current research also lies in the fact that most universities in Russia have conducted their research on terrorist groups deposited in their own prisons. American universities have also conducted the same type of research on groups and individuals that they consider terrorists, while to the researcher's knowledge there is a problem related to the scarcity of these studies in libraries. Iraqi.

Research Importance

The importance of studying the value trends and social beliefs underlying terrorist behavior was considered one of the strategic steps to confront the threat of terrorism (. В. Белашева, 2016: 18.). Recent studies have tended to research the growth of the five social beliefs, as they are common to cross-cultural human beings and were derived from more than forty different societies and cultures that represented samples that reflected the cognitive component behind these intuitions (ебедева Н.М.2008: 67).

Perhaps the importance of studying the five beliefs comes from the fact that they represent the prevailing general beliefs, which reflect the conflict between individuals and institutions within the same society. Exploitation, fundamentalism, and tolerance versus fanaticism, extremism and religiosity versus atheism and a lack of belief in the existence of a supreme will to run the world. Bond M.H, 2004 548-570). The importance of studying the trend of the growth of social beliefs gives clarity to the ideas and beliefs directed to the behavior of individuals as they are of value to others or pose a threat to them and it opens the doors of understanding and rapprochement and promotes the dialogue of civilizations just as it is used to fight extremist ideas and the behavior of terrorist groups (Журавлев). М, 2018: 341).

Search Limits

The current research is limited to those in the Nasiriyah Central Prison for the year 2017, and those sentenced to terrorism crimes.

Research Objectives

The current research aims to identify

1- The developmental characteristics of the social beliefs of the terrorist character.

2- The factors that dominate the beliefs of the terrorist personality.

Social Beliefs

Common beliefs that define the reality of individuals who live as ethnic, religious or national groups, and they believe that those beliefs distinguish them as a group show that group beliefs have behavioral, cognitive and emotional effects a task that reflects on the behavior of an individual as a member of the group to which he belongs. (Defined by Bond M.H., Leung K2011). They are general beliefs related to the self and others and the material and social world, and they represent the cognitive structures underlying beliefs and are based on a causal or correlation relationship between two ideas and do not include the values of right or wrong, some of which are positive (knowledge and good planning increase the success of the individual), and some of them are Negative (opportunistic and authoritarian behavior is the shortest way to success) and represent the five basic beliefs (reward for effort, social irony, resilience, belief in judgment, destiny, and religiosity). Beck JS, 2011 defined the social beliefs as basic, inflexible, absolute and general beliefs that people hold about themselves, others, the world and the future. The researcher adopted the definition of Bond M.H. and Leung K2011.

Theoretical Framework

Social Beliefs

Concept development

The concept is mainly due to the idea that each individual encounters a physical, social and spiritual world that requires its organization so that he has a space that enables him to coexist with others within his own culture or from other cultures.

This combination of the three worlds is related to the individual's ability to form internal and personal understandings and harmony, to be reflected in his dealings with the outside world and to produce an acceptable behavior that allows him to coexist and tolerate awareness, and on the contrary, it turns into a source of disability and then a threat to himself and others.

In this context, the value patterns and beliefs were studied by Rokeach (1973), and some sociologists tried to integrate culturally distinct values (for example (Kluckhohn1976 & Stodtbeck)), in studying the cognitive structure of the beliefs of people from different cultures. As for Schwartz, he tried to study the directed core values Behavior of individuals as beliefs that define their behavior (Schwartz, 1992: 104).

In 2008, Leung, Kwok & Bond, Michael Harris 2008 developed the concept of social beliefs with the aim of showing indications of that concept. They developed a program of inquiry and research, with the aim of studying (general beliefs). Social beliefs are general beliefs about the individual himself, about the social, material, and spiritual world, in a proof form between two concepts or existences.

In every culture there are multiple and divergent beliefs, and Leung, Kwok & Bond, Michael Harris have studied beliefs in cultures such as Canadian, American, European and Chinese, and they have given great importance to various sources such as (popular proverbs, stories and tales, newspapers, magazines, etc.), collecting More than (3000) beliefs, which were later divided into four types:

1. Psychological attribution or attribution: axioms that refer to the characteristics and goals of the personality.
2. Orientation towards a social world: axioms that refer to the characteristics of groups, groups and their organization.
3. Social interactions: intuitions about how people interact with each other.
4. The environment: axioms related to the surrounding medium, which has an effect on behavior.

These four broad styles were divided by scholars into (33) subtypes (in the Book of Social Beliefs). Items, use a five-tiered scale, with optional answers (I absolutely believe, I believe, I do not know, I do not believe, I do not believe at all).

In 2011, the owners of the scale developed (a survey of social beliefs), with the aim of issuing the final version consisting of (60) items, identified with five basic factors (social intuitions), and expressed on an individual or cultural level:

1. Social Cynicism - This factor includes items that represent a negative view of human nature, lack of confidence in the social world and the existing institutions, and that we live in a harsh world governed by the strong jungle law in which the weak eat, and even the laws are tricks that the influential people have put in place and do not apply them to themselves. .
2. Social Flexibility: The items of this factor indicate that there are no fixed rules, and there are multiple ways and methods to achieve results, and that the contradictions in the behavior of individuals are completely normal in everyday situations. This factor is related to the factor of openness to experience from the scale of personality factors The Big Five, it is also associated with cognitive complexity factor, and social intelligence.
3. Reward for Effort: In its clauses, there are grouping beliefs that fall under what indicates that good planning, knowledge, struggle and personal effort lead to positive results, and help to get rid of negative consequences, this factor is associated with belief in the justice of the world.

4. Religiosity and spiritual orientations: the items of this factor refer to belief in the existence of a higher will and powers that manage affairs, and that there is a great role for religiosity and religious commitment in determining and controlling behavior.
5. Self-control (belief in fate and fate): beliefs that indicate that all life events cause
6. There are predestined predecessors, and there are different ways that affect fate and destiny.

Chapter Three

Research Procedures

The third chapter includes research procedures, which include determining the research methodology, the research community, its sample, the research tool, and the statistical methods used in it.

1. Defining the research community

The current research community is determined by those in the central prison in DhiQar governorate who have been convicted of the crime of terrorism in accordance with Article 4 of the Anti-Terrorism Law and for security reasons, the total number of them has not been obtained.

2. Research sample

The sample of the research was 500 prisoners who were sentenced to various sentences, who were chosen randomly.

3. Research Tool

The researcher used the five cognitive axioms scale of Leung, Kwok & Bond, Michael Harris, 2011), and it consists of 60 items distributed into five domains, namely, (social irony, social flexibility, the reward for effort, religiosity and self-control) and for each area 12 items according to table (1) below.

Table (1) Items are detailed according to the factors

Items No.												Factor
58	56	52	43	39	34	28	22	20	17	12	9	Social irony
14	38	41	32	60	55	45	36	21	18	11	4	Reward for effort
19	13	10	57	51	49	47	42	24	16	8	5	Tolerance
1	53	46	44	35	33	30	26	23	15	7	2	Religiosity
3	59	54	50	48	40	37	31	29	27	25	6	Faith in destiny

4. The Psychometric Properties of The Scale

First: honesty

The global validity of the scale was extracted through the use of the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA-Analysis factor, Confirmatory), which according to Gardner.H (2001: 147) that its basis is the classification of variables. Before starting the factor analysis, it is necessary to make sure of the suitability of the sample size, and in order to verify this, the researcher extracted the Kaiser-Meyer Olkain test (KMO test). Since the basic theorizing of the scale has identified five factors considering that each cognitive axiom represents a factor of the overall characteristic, so the researcher used the basic components method and the Kaiser test and it was found that all of them obtained the latent root that is more than the correct one, then the researcher used the orthogonal rotation by the Varimax method and took a percentage A degree of (25,90) of the total size of the variance of factors and to determine the identity of the worker must be saturated with at least three significant items according to the criterion of Reeve, 2002)) and as indicated by the study (Al-Kanani 2011: 56), and Table (2) shows a presentation of the five factors.

Table (2) Items Saturation According to Factors

Special Variance	Explained variance	Fifth Factor	Fourth Factor	Third Factor	Second Factor	First Factor	Item
0.490916	0.503569	0.127689	0.502854	0.440378	0.465789	0.345609	1
0.579669	0.549102	0.438887 -	0.635600	0.490162	0.241029	0.470331	2
0.533882	0.533882	0.265017	0.282934	0.13106 9	0.236788	0.06047 -	3
0.675623	0.609610	0.301864	0.319709 7	0.008268	0.609125	-0.21958	4
0.460348	0.499628	-0.189072	0.470331	0.599293 7	0.107413 -	0.2100456	5
0.529669	0.620453	0.545018	0.529669	0.20453	0.34506	0.329669	6
0.470331	0.44106 9	0.008268	0.319709 7	0.214579	0.069107	-0.13182	7
0.436788	0.636823	0.371335	0.328665	0.559634	0.119040	0.219709 7	8
0732601	0.436823	0.271000	0.130095	0.327376	0.430117	0.7190235	9
0.528665	0.519634	0.311268	0.268091	0.4464097	0.351329	0.184924	10

0.633193	0.350246	0.171335	0.159634	0.328665	0.549464	0.264153 7	11
0.649754	0.366807	0.271569	0.130095	0.184924	0.130095	0.664153 7	12
0.613898	0.386102	0.300561	0.359634	0.550001	0.146407	0.378148	13
0.368879	0.631121	0.309812	0.351329	0.484924	0.184924	0.187961	14
0.537865	0.462135	0.130095	0.146457	0.327376	0.17961	0.275623	15
0.436986	0.563014	0.184924	0.130095	0.664153 7	0.438887 -	0.107413 -	16
0.518816	0.481184	0.328665	-0.024331	0.349012	0.466118	0.700145	17
0.591608	0.408392	0.159634	0.149464	0.230195	-0.51806 7	0.261113	18
0.653047	0.346953	0.328665	-0.18902	-0.21958	0.319709	0.282934	19
0.303533	0.696467	0.130095	0.275229	0.410725	-0.024231	0.569107	20
0.675623	0.264081	0.319709	0.396841	0.333882	0.179061	-0.131852	21
0.589275 -	0.069107	0.466118	0.259541	0.06047-	-0.21958	0.275229	22
0.773951	0.398996	0.265017	-0.18902	0.410725	0.496841	-0.13182	23
0.589275 -	0.533882	0.116802	0.099293	0.326049	0.346790	0.360470 -	24
0.773951	0.416802	0.461113	0.398996	0.315670	-0.01806	0.188834	25
0.589275 -	0.466118	-0.08582	-0.58582	0.275229	0.226049	0.410725	26
0.773951	0.398996	0.482934 0.365017	0.438887 -	0.361113	0.188834	0.116802	27
0.589275 -	0.596841	0.307413 -	0.230165	0.349102	0.226049	0.513094	28
0.773951	-0.618067	0.265017	0.188834	0.099293	-0.08582	0.466118	29
0.675623	-0.49958	0.359541	0.410725	0.433882	-0.18902	-0.018046	30
0.845254	0.254746	0.588834	0.099293	0.116802	0.226049	0.275229	31
0.533882	0.466118	-0.08582	0.538887 -	0.107413	0.4456789	0.490706	32
0.610725	0.409783	0.282934	0.461113	0.23015 -	0.349012	0.264153	33
0.589275	0.431669	0.417689	-0.13182	0.250539	-0.024361	0.569107	34
0.564710	0.437184 1	0.490706	0.509294 -	0.461531 -	0.211432 -	0.179601	35
0.561113	0.418887	0.319709	0.06047 -	0.2718056	0.710045	0.149464	36
0.51661	0.48339	0.107413	0.226049	0.438887 -	0.149464	-0.21916	37
0.686565	0.368879	-0.101641	0.241606	0.281218	0.492985	0.083845	38
0.530901	0.389108	0.241606	-0.108941	0.081845	0.339703	0.636646	39
0.49278	0.368879	0.631121	0.286565	0.137309	0.486565	- 0.107239	40
0.631121	0.368879	-0.104188	0.137309	0.483139	0.234790	0.063413	41
0.538121	0.368879	0.40875 8	0.310661	0.501934	0.281218	0.483319	42
0.710139	0.368879	0.339703	0.495779	0.028433	0.063413	0.495779	43
0.631121	0.368879	0.134689	0.1094561	0.292985	0.408765	0.404221	44
0.628433	0.495779	0.137309	0.028433	0.036646	0.563413	0.436646	45
0.588245	0.48339	0.104221	-0.504188	0.241606	0.408775	0.316003	46
0.492985	0.61218	0.316361	0.339703	0.504221	0.063413	0.495779	47
0.563014 -	0.480339	0.686565	0.216601	0.281218	0.339703	0.241606	48
0.553653	0.51661	0.186565	0.036646	0.563413	0.404221 0.028433	0.350612	49
0.563679	0.363679	0.363014 -	0.137309	0.072765	0.48339	0.339703	50
0.61845 1	0.456891	0.21845 1	0.072765	0.488455	0.40875 7	0.292985	51
0.772765	0.563014 -	0.436986	0.234567	0.236986	0.5567109	0.381218	52
0.663679	0.063821 -	0.436986	0.063821 -	0.130095	-0.11041	0.341606	53
0.496986	0.372765	0.063821 -	0.453653	0.21845 1	-0.104801	0.392985	54

0.559156	0.563014 -	0.436986	0.316601	0.408705	0.453653	0.207170	55
0.625941	0.063821 -	0.436986	-0.21845 1	0.363679	0.163014 -	0.507309	56
0.51845 1	0.399703	0.063821	0.253653	0.472765	0.259138	0.336170	57
0.4918451	0.363821 -	0.436986	0.263014 -	0.126043	0.553653	0.568331	58
0.553653	0.372765	0.363679	0.300170	0.163679	0.319541	0.372765	59
		0.310047	0.1300934	0.259541	0.610924	0.313709	60
		4.684191	4.852279	6.50815	8.616149	11.586383	Root Latent
		6.505821	6.739276	7.776181	7.952987	10.40053	Contrast percentage
		53.3748	32.86898	26.1297	18.35352	10.40053	Accumulative Percentage
		0.144372	0.149553	0.172563	0.176486	0.2308	Importance Relativity For the Factor

Through Table (2), we note that:

1. The observed saturations on the first factor, which were ± 0.50 (or more), with (9) items and their numbers (9,12,17,20,28,34,39,56,58).
2. The saturations observed on the second factor, which were ± 0.50 (or more), with (8) items and their numbers (4,11,18,21,36,45,55,60).
3. The saturations observed on the third factor, which were ± 0.50 (or more), with (6) items and their numbers (5,8,13,16,42,49).
4. The saturations observed on the fourth factor, which were ± 0.50 (or more), with (5) items and their numbers (1, 2, 26, 35, and 46).
5. The observed saturations on the fourth factor, which were ± 0.50 (or more), with (4) items and their numbers (6,31,40,48).

First: The Explanation of The Factors Extracted from The Factor Analysis

From Table (3) we notice that there are five factors that have increased the value of the root latent over the correct one, and that they explain the percentage (53.3748%) of the variance of grades for the five cognitive axioms scale, and that the ratio of the latent root of the first factor of the second factor amounted to 1.33) and it is the same for the second and third factors, which are Less than (2) in the sense that the scale does not tend to measure a dominant dimension at the expense of other dimensions, as Rekase (1977) stipulated that the criterion as a minimum for the validity of the scale in its inclusion of factors whose underlying roots are higher than the correct one.

The researcher adopted a criterion (± 30 more) as a criterion for accepting the saturation of paragraphs, according to Table (3):

Table (3) The Latent Roots According to The Number of items, Their Proportions and The Explained Variance

Total Items Percentage	Items Saturated No.	Explained Variance	Root Latent	Factor
53%	32	10.40053	11.586383	First
47%	28	7.952987	8.616149	Second
50%	30	7.776181	6.50815	Third
40%	24	6.739276	4.852	Fourth
55%	33	6.505821	4.684191	Fifth

From the table (3) we notice that all the five factors indicated acceptable percentages in terms of the percentage of paragraphs' contribution, which ranged from (38%- 55%) and this is another indicator of the validity of the scale, as these percentages are acceptable, with an average of 47%).In order to name the factors, it is necessary to determine the return of the paragraphs to the fields and according to the saturation section and to determine

their percentages from the total paragraphs included in the factor analysis and according to the following Table (4).

Table (4) Items Categorization by the factors and Percentage

Items	Factor	Items out of the overall number of items.
(9,12,17,20,28,34,39,56,58)	Social irony	75%
(4,11,18,21,36,45,55,60)	Reward for effort	67%
(5,8,13,16, ,42,49)	Tolerance	50%
(1,2,26,35,46,.)	Religiosity	42%
(6,31,40,48)	Faith in destiny	25%

Based on the aforementioned interpretation of the extracted factors, the results, as a whole, indicate the validity and accuracy of the five cognitive axioms scale in terms of its hypothetical composition to measure what was set for it.

Second. Consistency:

The researcher used the Cronbach coefficient to verify the stability of the scale, which measures the internal consistency of the paragraphs, considering that each item is an independent measure that tends to measure the same feature (Hakkat, 2012: 375).

Chapter Four: Presentation of Results

First. Objectives The developmental characteristics of the terrorist personality's social beliefs. The results of the factor analysis showed that the factors with a latent root (1) were greater than five factors, as in the table below:

Table (5): Factor Analysis Results

Total Percentage	Items	Items Saturated No.	Explained Variance	Root Latent	Factor
53%		32	10.40053	11.586383	First
47%		28	7.952987	8.616149	Second
50%		30	7.776181	6.50815	Third
40%		24	6.739276	4.852	Fourth
55%		33	6.505821	4.684191	Fifth

From the above table it becomes clear that the percentage of the contribution of these five factors amounted to (87.751% of the characteristic to be measured, which is a very high percentage, and as is also evident from the above table) that the percentage of variance explained for the first factor (social irony) reached (31,640), which is the highest percentage compared to the factors. The other four and the other four factors came after him in succession, as he (Tigaza, 2012: 96-9) refers to the test of the interpreted contrast, and the importance of this method lies in the fact that it emphasizes the practical or practical importance of the ability of the selected factors to comprehend or represent the information or determine Results The number of factors that explain a contrast ratio of 50 to 90%, and the best method is to extract the one that explains the largest possible amount of variance with the least number of factors.

Scree Chart: A diabetes chart is one of the results of the factor analysis and reflects the vector of the weak factors and their slope towards the x-axis, and the direction of the dominant factors towards the y-axis, (Ledesma, RD, 2007: 12)) and it appears from the chart below the dominance of the first factor (social irony) and the second factor (intolerance) Tolerance versus tolerance), and the decline of other factors (religiosity, effort towards reward, and belief in fate) as they did not constitute an effective percentage of the measured trait.

The developmental characteristics of the development of the five cognitive axioms can be explained according

to the theorizing on which the standard adopted in the current research is based:

- 1- Irony came first, and it is a cognitive structure that indicates the growth of beliefs represented in the lack of belief of their owners in the prevailing moral determinants and that laws are nothing but tricks developed by the strong to exploit the weak, and that the world in which we live is based on the law of the jungle and the principle of (large fish devour small fish) Fraud, fraud and exploitation of others is the best and shortest path to success.
- 2- As for the cognitive structure that came in the second rank, it is related to the first in terms of growth. The adopted theorizing indicates that the prevalence of irony leads to the belief that the effort exerted is not appreciated by others and that planning, knowledge and knowledge are only slow and costly ways to obtain rewards or profits and that there are ways Shorter and faster, the use of force, tricks, deception, shadowing others, blurring the vision, and preventing people from relying on fixed values and clear logic make them accept what is gradually happening to them.
- 3- The third cognitive axiom that relates to the above axioms, as intolerance and prejudice grow without scrutiny and forcing others to adopt others 'plans and opinions by force, instead of tolerance, compassion and affection, and instead of adhering to the laws and values that promote living and coexistence in peace, cognitive structures that generate threatening, intimidating and terror behaviors are common.
- 4- The principle of religiosity, respect for the opposite opinion and bearing the positions of others and their vision of the world is incompatible with all the foregoing cognitive axioms that are based on exploitation, cynicism and intolerance, and false ideas are generated and developed about religiosity as a feature that organizes life and directs behavior and contributes to coexistence and acceptance, and instead turns into a wrong understanding and extremist ideas allow killing and terrorizing others.

- 5- As for the axiom that came in the last place, it relies on a positive principle that differentiates between everything that happens to a person can be controlled by his adoption of knowledge, knowledge and laws that regulate his life and his enjoyment of tolerance in exchange for the belief that everything that happens to a person is a predetermined fate and that it is not The benefit of claiming that we control our destinies, therefore, one has to win quickly without regard for the consequences and morals of that gain.

The Factors That Dominate the Beliefs of The Terrorist Personality

To find out which factors dominate the beliefs of the terrorist personality, the researcher calculated the average answers to the paragraphs in each field, which he included in Table (6), where it was found that social irony is the most dominant factor over beliefs and it is related to not recognizing all the existing systems and laws and the logic of Power is the best way to achieve goals as the focus is not on the ethics of means, and the more cynicism the less religiosity and belief that there is a higher will that controls the universe, and thus (sarcasm and its antithesis, religiosity) is the most dominant factor, as each occupied the first and last places and came the factor (fanaticism versus Fatalism) as a factor also plays a major role in the Five-Belief System.

Table (6) Average Items answers for each field

No.	Factor	Average of Study Sample Alternatives
1	Social irony	4 , 6
2	Reward for effort	3 , 4
3	Tolerance	3 , 2
4	Religiosity	2
5	Faith in destiny	1 , 4

Conclusions

1. Personality traits grow gradually and according to the influence of social and economic factors, as well as the imagination, value system, and cognitive intuitions that are reflected in the behavior of individuals, their attitudes and attitudes.
2. The developmental characteristics of cognitive intuitions are the product of cognitive growth and the value system related to the individual's belief in the existing laws and his constant and relatively constant feeling of the importance of the law, and that the individual's relationship with others is determined to be safe and stable or threatened and anxious according to the type of environment and social relationships that are among the determinants of the growth of social beliefs.
3. The importance of knowledge, planning and the investment of knowledge grows under the attractive circumstances, while expelling it produces nothing but exploitation, deception and the adoption of immoral or legitimate means
4. Intolerance and extremism are traits that grow along with exploitation and fraud.
5. Terrorist behavior grows with extremism and a misconception of religion and is paralleled by the sense that strength, vulnerability and terror of others is the best way to achieve goals.

Recommendations

1. Adopting psychological studies in understanding and deconstructing the beliefs that underlie terrorist behavior.
2. Combating extremist ideology and ideas that encourage the emergence of exploitation.

Suggestions

1. Benefiting from the results of the current research in dealing with terrorism as a concept and behavior.
2. Conducting studies by accrediting a team of researchers regarding terrorist behavior and terrorist personality.

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